

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

A novel pathway for regeneration in the vertebrate spinal cord.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We measured total transcription in the spinal cord of an amphibian that has native (endogenous) regenerative capacity in the central nervous system to discover factors associated with regeneration in the CNS. Humans do not have endogenous regenerative capacity in the CNS.

We identified specific activation of the clotting factor F13b following traumatic resection of the spinal cord, at day 3 and day 6 post-injury.

The pathway consisted of F13b likely in conjunction with clotting factors F11, F2 and F7, von Willebrand factors Vwa3a and Vwa3b, complement cascade effectors C9, C8a and C8b and potentially lipoprotein A [Lp(a)].

Results

The pathway consisted of F13b likely in conjunction with clotting factors F11, F2 and F7, von Willebrand factors Vwa3a and Vwa3b, complement cascade effectors C9, C8a and C8b and potentially lipoprotein A [Lp(a)], which we judged in part based on specific co-regulation with F13b in human cells and tissues.

Myogenic and neurogenic factors

1. Myf5
2. MyoD1
3. Neurod6
4. Neurod4
5. Neurog1
6. Adig

Chemokines and Cytokines

1. Il36rn
2. Il36b
3. Il5ra
4. Il22
5. Il17a
6. Ccl16

Soluble Factors

1. IHH
2. Fgf5
3. Fgf23
4. Fgf20
5. Fgf5
6. Fgf6
7. Npvf
8. Wnt8b
9. Bmp15
10. Ifna5
11. Ifna21
12. Ifna2
13. Ifnw1

Pluripotency and re-programming

1. Klf16
2. Klf17
3. Pou1f1
4. Pou3f4
5. Pou6f2
6. Nodal
7. NOBOX
8. Esrrb

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Homeobox transcription factors

- 1. Tbr1 (brain-specific T-box)
- 2. Anhx
- 3. Tbx5
- 4. Tbx5
- 5. Tbx10
- 6. Gata4
- 7. Pax3
- 8. Pax4
- 9. Sox10
- 10. Sox11
- 11. Sox14
- 12. Sox15
- 13. Olig2
- 14. Dlx2
- 15. Pdx1
- 16. Hmgb4
- 17. Cdx1
- 18. Cdx4
- 19. Prop1
- 20. Onecut1/2
- 21. Hnf1b
- 22. Alx1
- 23. Ventxp1
- 24. Tbx4
- 25. Hoxc8
- 26. Six6
- 27. Tlx2
- 28. Phox2b

Zygotic activation or sperm cell

- 1. Zpbp
- 2. Eddma3a
- 3. Cylc1
- 4. Spam1
- 5. PZP

1 Immune Receptors and Immunity

- 2 1. Ctla4
3 2. DCSTAMP
4 3. Fcrl4
5 4. MIA2
6 5. Ncr1
7 6. Fndc7
8 7. Prss37
9 8. Clec1b
10 9. Clec4d
11 10. Clec4m
12 11. Rhesus factor Rhbg
13 12. Rhesus factor Rhag

14 Liver

- 15 1. Fibrinogen alpha FGA
16 2. FGB
17 3. FGG
18 4. Albumin ALB
19 5. Hfe2
20 6. ITIH family genes

21 Regeneration, repair and wound healing

- 22 1. Tenascin R (TNR)
23 2. Tenascin N (TNR)
24 3. Reg1p
25 4. Reg3a
26 5. Reg3g

27 Angiogenesis

- 28 1. Angptl3

29 Visual system

- 30 1. MIP
31 2. Nyx
32 3. Vsx1
33 4. CRX
34 5. Rhodopsin
35 6. Nrl
36 7. Pmpg1

37 **Discussion**

38 We provided evidence here for the existence of a novel regenerative response in the vertebrate spinal cord characterized by expression of the clotting factor F13b, identified using a salamander model of spinal cord injury; this organism possesses unusual endogenous CNS regenerative capacity.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Methods

We used whole transcriptome technologies together with R-based computational methods and SEEK for this study of regeneration in the CNS.